

Horizon 2020 ULTRAWAVE

Ultra capacity wireless layer beyond 100 GHz based on millimetre wave Traveling Wave Tubes

WP7. Deliverable D7.2: ULTRAWAVE Website

Start date of project: 01.09.2017

Duration: 36 months

Project no: 762119

Project acronym: **ULTRAWAVE**

Deliverable deadline: **30th November 2017**

Deliverable Submission: **29st November 2017**

Organisation name of lead contractor for this report: Universidad Politécnic de Valencia, Spain

Dissemination level

PU	Public	X
PP	Restricted to other programme participants (including Commission Services)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Commission Services)	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services)	

Table of Contents

1. INTRODUCTION	4
2. GENERAL STRUCTURE OF THE WEBSITE	4
3. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE UPGRADES.....	11

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

ULTRAWAVE consortium is fully aware of the importance of a wide dissemination of the activities and results of the project by web and social media.

The website of the H2020 ULTRAWAVE project is available at <http://www.ultrawave2020.eu/> since September, 2017.

This report describes the website sections and provides an overview of its contents. In particular, the website has a public part to facilitate the dissemination of project's information to different stakeholders, a private part, accessible only by consortium members, dedicated to information exchange between partners and a reserved area for the EU Commission.

1. INTRODUCTION

The ULTRAWAVE website aims to attract the interest of the widest audience with sections oriented to the general public and sections with more specialist contents oriented to inform industry, scientific community, end users such as telecom operators, and standardization bodies.

The ULTRAWAVE website has a public area and a restricted, password protected area.

The ULTRAWAVE public website is the core element of the project's dissemination strategy and is intended to provide a vision of the project and general information about the main activities and results achieved with the objective to:

- Raise awareness about the project activities
- Facilitate the diffusion of the project's results
- Promote their industrial exploitation

The restricted area includes two password protected sections to share files with the reviewers and the European Commission and among partners.

A further password protected collaborative space is hosted in the LUBox portal of Lancaster University for sharing and storing files and use of collaborative sheets.

2. GENERAL STRUCTURE OF THE WEBSITE

The URL of the website is <http://www.ultrawave2020.eu/> and is online since September 2017. The website is hosted and maintained by UPV and will be updated regularly with scientific results, findings and achievements.

The ULTRAWAVE public area is composed of a home-page, that shortly introduces the project and where the user can find the latest news and upcoming events, and a menu structured according to the following navigation points:

- About
- Technology
- Results
- Links
- News & Events
- Media
- Contact

A screenshot of the website home page is shown in Fig. 1.

Project

The ULTRAWAVE project is aimed at developing a high capacity backhaul that enables 5G cell densification by exploiting bands beyond 100 GHz. New travelling wave tubes delivering high power will allow the creation of an ultra capacity layer providing more than 100 Gbps per kilometer square in Point to Multi point at D-band (141 – 174.8 GHz) fed by novel G-band (300 GHz) Point to Point high capacity links. The ULTRAWAVE system is empowered by the convergence of three main technologies: vacuum electronics, solid-state electronics and photonics. This ULTRAWAVE layer will enable backhaul of hundreds of small and pico cells,

EVENTS

IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference – WCNC 2018
15 April 2018 to 18 April 2018
Barcelona (Spain)
CALL FOR PAPER Special Session Workshop:
Economics and Adoption of Millimeter Wave Technology in Future Networks.

Fig. 1. ULTRAWAVE website

A brief description of each website section is given below.

- **Section “About”.** In this section a summary of the ULTRAWAVE project, including the context and the main objectives to be addressed, is provided. Moreover, it presents the institutions as well as organizations involved in the project and gives a short description of the work plan with information about the specific objectives, and leaders of each work package. Fig. 2 shows a screenshot of the Project Description Section.

Project Description

For the first time, smartphones and tablets data usage exceeds desktops. This is a wake up call for manufacturers and operators to provide users with ubiquitous, high speed and high quality wireless coverage. The 5G cell densification is the only available route due to the constraints of sub-6GHz networks. A dense deployment of small cells requires a capillary backhaul and novel approaches to fronthaul.

While the increase of data rate at small cell level has found solutions, the quest for high-density backhaul remains still unanswered. The fiber is too expensive and of difficult deployment. The wireless backhaul is the preferred solution for operators for performance, flexibility and cost. The traffic demand requires an upshift from microwave to high capacity millimeter wave backhaul, and overcome the current technology limits.

ULTRAWAVE responds to the challenge of high capacity, high cell density backhaul by proposing, for the first time, the exploitation of the whole millimeter wave spectrum beyond 100 GHz. This will be used to create an ultra capacity layer providing more than 100 Gbps/km² in Point to Multi point at D-band (141 – 174.8 GHz) over 500 m radius of coverage, fed by novel G-band (300 GHz) Point to Point high capacity links with more than 600 m range.

EVENTS

IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference - WCNC 2018
15 April 2018 to 18 April 2018
Barcelona (Spain)
CALL FOR PAPER Special Session Workshop: Economics and Adoption of Millimeter Wave Technology in Future Networks.

Kickoff Meeting
14 September 2017 to 15 September 2017
Lancaster University (UK)

Engineers to pioneer unprecedented high speed

Fig. 2. Project Description

- **Section “Technology”.** This section introduces the main technological challenges to be faced by the project. This section will be updated during the lifetime of the project with the main technological achievement obtained. Fig. 3 shows the Technology section.

ULTRAWAVE: About Technology Results Links News & Events Media Contact

The main technological advancements and challenges of the project are:

Traveling wave tubes amplifiers (TWT)

Traveling Wave Tubes are the only devices able to provide power at Watt level in a multi GHz band at millimetre waves. Two novel TWTs will be designed and realized at D-band (141 – 148.5 GHz) and G-band (275 – 305 GHz) respectively to enable the ULTRAWAVE ultra capacity layer. Technologies and process at the state of the art will be adopted. The TWTs will be designed and fabricated at Lancaster University, UK, in collaboration with Goethe University of Frankfurt, Germany and HF Systems Engineering GmbH, Germany.

6 Feb 2017
Terahertz wireless links could enable 10x 5G data rates over 300-GHz band: Researchers Hiroshima University, Japan's National Institute of Information and Communications Technology, and Panasonic Corporation have announced the development of a terahertz (THz) transmitter capable of transmitting digital data at a rate exceeding 100 gigabits (= 0.1 terabit) per second over a single channel using the 300-GHz band.

1 Feb 2017
Microwave backhaul evolution reaching beyond 100 GHz
Microwave backhaul technology plays a significant role in providing reliable mobile network performance and is well prepared to support both the evolution of LTE and the introduction of 5G.

Fig. 2 Traveling Wave Tube Concept

Fig. 3. ULTRAWAVE Technology

- **Section “Results”**. This section records all the research papers, related to the project, published by partners on scientific journals and conference proceedings as well as the presentations performed. The public deliverables released during the project are listed in the sub-section Deliverables. On the other hand, newsletters and other dissemination material will be posted here to be downloaded for ULTRAWAVE website users.

Fig. 4. Presentations Section

- **Section “Links”**. This page shows the links to other projects and organisations in relation with ULTRAWAVE for common activities or cooperation; for instance, regarding joint workshops.
- **Section “News & Events”**. This page shows news, and upcoming events related to ULTRAWAVE. For example, a list of conferences or workshops dedicated to particular sub-domains of the project goals will be announced in this section. Fig. 5 shows the News section.

News

06 February 2017

Terahertz wireless links could enable 10x 5G data rates over 300-GHz band: Researchers

Hiroshima University, Japan's National Institute of Information and Communications Technology, and Panasonic Corporation have announced the development of a terahertz (THz) transmitter capable of transmitting digital data at a rate exceeding 100 gigabits (= 0.1 terabit) per second over a single channel using the 300-GHz band.

01 February 2017

Microwave backhaul evolution reaching beyond 100 GHz

Microwave backhaul technology plays a significant role in providing reliable mobile network performance and is well prepared to support both the evolution of LTE and the introduction of 5G. Work has now started

EVENTS

IEEE Wireless Communications and Networking Conference - WCNC 2018
15 April 2018 to 18 April 2018
Barcelona (Spain)
CALL FOR PAPER Special Session Workshop: Economics and Adoption of Millimeter Wave Technology in Future Networks.

Kickoff Meeting
14 September 2017 to 15 September 2017
Lancaster University (UK)

Engineers to pioneer unprecedented high speed

Fig. 5. News Section

- **Section "Media"**. This page shows the material available for distribution through the media as e.g. press releases, videos, etc.

Fig. 6. Media Section

- **Section “Contact”**. This section provides the contact details of the ULTRAWAVE Coordinator in case the website users want to get further information about the project.

A link to the ULTRAWAVE collaborative platform used for internal communication is available at the bottom of the home page. This private area is password-protected reserved to project partners.

The objective of this area is, in addition to the LUBox space, to have a second secure and private place to share documents between partners and a special section, in the form of forum, to have discussion about issues arising from the different work packages. This area will also be used to keep working versions of documents such as on-going version of reports and deliverables and to have a repository of deliverables, meeting minutes and all documents relevant to the project.

A “Reviewers area” is set for file exchange with the project officer and the reviewers. A login and a password will be provided shortly. Fig. 7 shows the Reviewers Area.

The image shows a login form for the 'ULTRAWAVE REVIEWERS AREA'. At the top, there is a logo with the text 'ULTRAWAVE' in blue and 'REVIEWERS AREA' in black, with a magnifying glass icon over the 'E' in 'ULTRAWAVE'. Below the logo, there are two input fields: one for 'Username' and one for 'Password'. To the right of the password field is a blue button with the text 'Sign in'. Below the button, there is a link for 'Forgotten Password?' and a note: 'Please contact with sysadmin@ntc.upv.es'.

Fig. 7. Reviewers Area

Finally, the home page has also links to Twitter and LinkedIn accounts of the project (Fig. 8 and Fig. 9).

Fig. 8. Twitter profile of the project

Fig. 9. LinkedIn group for ULTRAWAVE

3. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE UPGRADES

The first release of public website and private area for the ULTRAWAVE project are on line.

The website provides the initial set of information about the project and will be regularly updated to report the progresses and the activity of the project. A web tracker as e.g. Google Analytics providing web statistics will be used to assess the website visibility and make website improvements based on this information.